

Associations of selected atypical non-neuroendocrine cancers with multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1

Running title: cancer in MEN1 syndrome

Keywords: MEN1, breast cancer, thyroid cancer, renal cancer

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Supplementary materials

Table S1. Fraction of participants with available data for each given parameter for the study population, males and females.

Variable	Study population n/total n	Males n/total n	Females n/total n
Number of patients (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
Number of males (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
Number of females (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
Age at MEN-1 diagnosis (years)	110/113	49/51	61/62
Predisposing mutation (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
pHPT (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
pHPT diagnosis age years (years)	107/111	49/50	58/61
PNET (n)	104/113	46/51	58/62
PNET diagnosis age years (years)	66/70	32/33	34/37
DNET (n)	107/113	48/51	59/62
DNET diagnosis age years (years)	8/10	4/6	4/4
Other NET (n)	111/113	50/51	61/62
Other NET diagnosis age (years)	12/13	7/7	5/6
PitNET (n)	106/113	48/51	58/62
PitNET diagnosis age (years)	33/33	12/12	21/21
AdrT (n)	111/113	50/51	61/62
AdrT diagnosis age (years)	32/33	13/14	19/19
PTC (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
PTC diagnosis age (years)	7/7	2/2	5/5
BC (n)	111/113	50/51	61/62
BC diagnosis age years (years)	7/7	NA	7/7
RC (n)	113/113	51/51	62/62
RC diagnosis age years (years)	5/5	3/3	2/2

pHPT; primary hyperparathyroidism, PNET; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumour, DNET; duodenal neuroendocrine tumour, NET; neuroendocrine tumour, MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1, PitNET; pituitary neuroendocrine tumour, AdrT; adrenal tumor, BC; breast cancer, RC; renal cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, NA; not applicable

Table S2. Characteristics of the study population according to breast cancer status.

	No breast cancer n (%) / mean (SD)	Breast cancer n (%) / mean (SD)	<i>P</i>
Number of patients (n)	104 (93.7)	7 (6.3)	
Number of males (n)	50 (48.1)	0 (0.0)	
Number of females (n)	54 (51.9)	7 (11.5)	0.013
Predisposing mutation (n)			0.014
c.1356_1367del12	67 (64.4)	5 (71.4)	
c.1252G>A	1 (1.0)	1 (14.3)	
c.1546dup	26 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	
c.1579C>T	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.13_15delinsACGCT	1 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	
c.466G>C	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	
c.778C>T	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.894-895del	1 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	
c.417C>A	1 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	
c.1064G>A	1 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	
Not defined	2 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	
Age at MEN-1 diagnosis (years)	41.4 (15.4)	40.6 (14.3)	0.89
pHPT (n)	102 (98.1)	7 (100.0)	0.71
pHPT diagnosis age years (years)	40.4 (13.7)	36.5 (11.9)	0.47
PNET (n)	67 (69.1)	3 (50.0)	0.33
PNET diagnosis age years (years)	47.0 (13.5)	49.1 (11.7)	0.79
DNET (n)	10 (10.1)	0 (0.0)	0.41
DNET diagnosis age years (years)	62.2 (10.9)	NA	NA
Other NET (n)	13 (12.7)	0 (0.0)	0.31
Other NET diagnosis age (years)	50.6 (12.4)	NA	NA
PitNET (n)	30 (30.6)	2 (28.6)	0.89
PitNET diagnosis age (years)	39.6 (14.8)	37.7 (13.9)	0.91
AdrT (n)	30 (29.4)	2 (28.6)	0.96
AdrT diagnosis age (years)	51.0 (8.6)	49.9 (8.5)	0.86
BC (n)	0 (0.0)	7 (6.3)	NA
BC diagnosis age (years)	NA	49.9 (10.8)	NA
PTC (n)	5 (4.8)	2 (28.6)	0.012
PTC diagnosis age (years)	44.6 (16.5)	43.7 (23.5)	0.95
RC (n)	4 (3.8)	1 (14.3)	0.197
RC diagnosis age (years)	57.6 (18.1)	67.5 (0.0)	0.66

The numbers indicate mean (SD) for continuous variables and number of observations (percentage) for categorical variables. *P* is given for statistical comparison between those with and those without breast cancer. MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1, pHPT; primary hyperparathyroidism, PNET; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumour, DNET; duodenal neuroendocrine tumour, NET; neuroendocrine tumour, PitNET; pituitary neuroendocrine tumour, AdrT; adrenal tumour, BC; breast cancer, RC; renal cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, NA; not applicable

Table S3. Characteristics of the study population according to papillary thyroid carcinoma status.

	No PTC n (%) / mean (SD)	PTC n (%) / mean (SD)	<i>P</i>
Number of patients (n)	106 (93.8)	7 (6.2)	
Number of males (n)	49 (46.2)	2 (28.6)	
Number of females (n)	57 (53.8)	5 (71.4)	
Predisposing mutation (n)			0.001
c.1356_1367del12	71 (67.0)	2 (28.6)	
c.1252G>A	1 (0.9)	1 (14.3)	
c.1546dup	24 (22.6)	2 (28.6)	
c.1579C>T	1 (0.9)	1 (14.3)	
c.13_15delinsACGCT	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.466G>C	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.778C>T	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.894-895del	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.417C>A	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.1064G>A	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	
Not defined	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
Age at MEN-1 diagnosis (years)	41.4 (15.5)	42.4 (17.3)	0.89
pHPT (n)	104 (98.1)	7 (100.0)	0.71
pHPT diagnosis age years (years)	40.1 (13.6)	38.7 (13.9)	0.79
PNET (n)	67 (69.1)	3 (42.9)	0.15
PNET diagnosis age years (years)	47.3 (13.5)	40.1 (4.4)	0.45
DNET (n)	10 (10.0)	0 (0.0)	0.38
DNET diagnosis age years (years)	62.2 (10.9)	NA	NA
Other NET (n)	13 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	0.32
Other NET diagnosis age (years)	50.6 (12.4)	NA	NA
PitNET (n)	29 (29.3)	3 (42.9)	0.49
PitNET diagnosis age (years)	39.3 (14.9)	41.4 (12.0)	0.68
AdrT (n)	32 (30.8)	1 (14.3)	0.36
AdrT diagnosis age (years)	51.6 (9.1)	47.5 (0.0)	0.66
BC (n)	5 (4.8)	2 (28.6)	0.012
BC diagnosis age (years)	48.2 (12.0)	54.5 (8.6)	0.56
PTC (n)	0 (0.0)	7 (100.0)	0.36
PTC diagnosis age (years)	NA	44.4 (16.6)	NA
RC (n)	4 (3.8)	1 (14.3)	0.19
RC diagnosis age (years)	57.6 (18.1)	67.5 (0.0)	0.66

The numbers indicate mean (SD) for continuous variables and number of observations (percentage) for categorical variables. *P* is given for statistical comparison between those with and those without thyroid cancer. MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1, pHPT; primary hyperparathyroidism, PNET; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumour, DNET; duodenal neuroendocrine tumour, NET; neuroendocrine tumour, PitNET; pituitary neuroendocrine tumour, AdrT; adrenal tumour, BC; breast cancer, RC; renal cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, NA; not applicable

Table S4. Characteristics of the study population according to renal cancer status.

	No renal cancer n (%) / mean (SD)	Renal cancer n (%) / mean (SD)	<i>P</i>
Number of patients (n)	108 (95.6)	5 (4.4)	
Number of males (n)	48 (44.4)	3 (60.0)	
Number of females (n)	60 (55.6)	2 (40.0)	
Predisposing mutation (n)			0.38
c.1356_1367del12	69 (63.9)	4 (80.0)	
c.1252G>A	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.1546dup	26 (24.1)	0 (0.0)	
c.1579C>T	1 (0.9)	1 (20.0)	
c.13_15delinsACGCT	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.466G>C	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.778C>T	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.894-895del	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.417C>A	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
c.1064G>A	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	
Not defined	2 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	
Age at MEN-1 diagnosis (years)	40.9 (15.2)	53.5 (19.9)	0.08
pHPT (n)	106 (98.1)	5 (100.0)	0.76
pHPT diagnosis age years (years)	39.8 (13.2)	44.1 (21.1)	0.49
PNET (n)	68 (68.7)	2 (40.0)	0.18
PNET diagnosis age years (years)	47.1 (13.4)	48.1 (15.9)	0.92
DNET (n)	10 (9.8)	0 (0.0)	0.46
DNET diagnosis age years (years)	62.2 (10.9)	NA	NA
Other NET (n)	12 (11.3)	1 (20.0)	0.56
Other NET diagnosis age (years)	50.1 (12.9)	55.6 (0.0)	0.70
PitNET (n)	32 (31.4)	0 (0.0)	0.16
PitNET diagnosis age (years)	39.5 (14.5)	NA	NA
AdrT (n)	31 (29.2)	2 (40.0)	0.61
AdrT diagnosis age (years)	51.2 (9.1)	55.5 (5.4)	0.52
BC (n)	6 (5.7)	1 (20.0)	0.49
BC diagnosis age (years)	48.2 (10.8)	60.3 (0.0)	0.35
PTC (n)	6 (5.6)	1 (20.0)	0.20
PTC diagnosis age (years)	41.7 (16.4)	60.4 (0.0)	0.34
RC (n)	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)	0.19
RC diagnosis age (years)	NA	59.6 (16.3)	NA

The numbers indicate mean (SD) for continuous variables and number of observations (percentage) for categorical variables. *P* is given for statistical comparison between those with and those without thyroid cancer. MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1, pHPT; primary hyperparathyroidism, PNET; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumour, DNET; duodenal neuroendocrine tumour, NET; neuroendocrine tumour, PitNET; pituitary neuroendocrine tumour, AdrT; adrenal tumour, BC; breast cancer, RC; renal cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, NA; not applicable

Table S5. Number of selected cancers, ages of diagnosis and follow-up times in the MEN1 and OPERA cohorts.

	MEN1 cohort	OPERA cohort	<i>P</i>
All participants			
Number of participants n (%)	113 (100.0)	1045 (100.0)	<0.001
Follow-up time (years)	56.1 (17.1)	73.6 (6.6)	<0.001
BC n (%)	7 (6.2)	33 (3.2)	0.097
Age at BC diagnosis (years)	49.9 (10.8)	62.2 (8.5)	0.002
PTC n (%)	7 (6.2)	11 (1.1)	<0.001
Age at PTC diagnosis (years)	44.4 (16.6)	49.6 (7.8)	0.38
RC n (%)	5 (4.4)	13 (1.2)	0.025
Age at RC diagnosis (years)	59.6 (16.3)	58.8 (13.1)	0.91
Males			
Number of males n (%)	51 (45.1)	520 (49.8)	<0.001
Follow-up time (years)	54.3 (14.9)	73.8 (6.3)	<0.001
BC n (%)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	NA
Age at BC diagnosis (years)	NA	NA	NA
PTC n (%)	2 (3.9)	6 (1.2)	0.155
Age at PTC diagnosis (years)	56.1 (17.4)	49.0 (4.4)	0.33
RC n (%)	3 (5.9)	7 (1.3)	0.051
Age at RC diagnosis (years)	52.2 (17.8)	65.6 (6.7)	0.11
Females			
Number of females n (%)	62 (54.9)	525 (50.2)	<0.001
Follow-up time (years)	57.6 (18.6)	73.3 (6.9)	<0.001
BC n (%)	7 (11.5)	33 (6.3)	0.172
Age at BC diagnosis (years)	49.9 (10.8)	62.2 (8.5)	<0.001
PTC n (%)	5 (8.1)	5 (1.0)	0.002
Age at PTC diagnosis (years)	39.7 (15.5)	50.3 (11.2)	0.25
RC n (%)	2 (3.2)	6 (1.1)	0.203
Age at RC diagnosis (years)	70.6 (4.4)	50.8 (14.7)	<0.001

BC; breast cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, RC; renal cancer

Table S6. Hazard ratios for selected cancers, for subjects belonging to the MEN1 cohort compared to the OPERA cohort.

All participants	HR (95% CI)
BC	4.48 (1.97 - 10.18)
PTC	9.37 (3.59 - 24.41)
RC	7.80 (2.74 - 22.25)
Males	
BC	NA
PTC	5.74 (1.14 - 28.8)
RC	12.35 (3.10 - 49.17)
Females	
BC	3.79 (1.66 - 8.60)
PTC	12.87 (3.70 - 45.03)
RC	5.18 (1.03 - 26.14)

BC; breast cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid carcinoma, RC; renal cancer

Information on missing data - **Table S1**

Descriptive data on genetic and endocrine characteristics of patients with MEN1 - **Table 1**

Counts of all endocrine and non-endocrine tumors in patients with MEN1 - **Table 2**

Descriptive data of MEN1 patients with selected non-endocrine cancers - **Table 3**

- Comparison of MEN1 patients with BC with MEN1 patients without BC - **Table S2**

- One-way ANOVA (normally distributed, continuous)

- Kruskal-Wallis test (non-normally distributed, continuous)

- Pearson chi-square test (categorical)

- Comparison of MEN1 patients with PTC with MEN1 patients without PTC - **Table S3**

- Comparison of MEN1 patients with RC with MEN1 patients without RC - **Table S4**

Descriptive clinical data of MEN1 patients diagnosed with BC - **Table 4**

Descriptive clinical data of MEN1 patients diagnosed with PTC - **Table 5**

Descriptive clinical data of MEN1 patients diagnosed with RC - **Table 6**

KM curves and crude Cox regression models for BC (A), PTC (B) and RC (C) - **Figure 1**

- Descriptive data on events and follow-up times - **Table S5**

- Hazard ratios of selected cancers for MEN1 patients cohort compared to controls - **Table S6**

- Sex-specific KM-curves and crude Cox regression models for females - **Figure S2**

- Sex-specific KM-curves and crude Cox regression models for males - **Figure S3**

Figure S1. Flow chart representing the study population and analyses done. OPERA; Oulu Project Elucidating Risk of Atherosclerosis, MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1, pHPT; primary hyperparathyroidism, PNET; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumor, DNET; duodenal neuroendocrine tumor, NET; neuroendocrine tumor, PitNET; pituitary neuroendocrine tumor, AdrT; adrenal tumor, BC; breast cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid cancer, RC; renal cancer, KM; Kaplan-Meier.

Figure S2. Cumulative hazard of (A) breast cancer, (B) thyroid cancer and (C) renal cancer in females of the MEN1 cohort (red) and in the OPERA cohort (black). HR (95% CI) and P are given for diagnosis of MEN1 in a pooled cohort in unadjusted Cox regression. MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia 1, BC; breast cancer, PTC; papillary thyroid cancer, RC; renal cancer, OPERA; Oulu Project Elucidating Risk of Atherosclerosis, HR; Hazard ratio, CI; Confidence Interv

Figure S3. Cumulative hazard of (A) thyroid cancer and (B) renal cancer in males of the MEN1 cohort (red) and in the OPERA cohort (black). HR (95% CI) and P are given for diagnosis of MEN1 in a pooled cohort in unadjusted Cox regression. MEN1; multiple endocrine neoplasia 1, PTC; papillary thyroid cancer, RC; renal cancer, OPERA; Oulu Project Elucidating Risk of Atherosclerosis, HR; Hazard ratio, CI; Confidence Interval.